

TEACHERS' READING STRATEGIES: ITS EFFECT ON LEARNERS' READING PERFORMANCE

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Teachers' Reading Strategies: Its Effect on Learners' Reading Performance

Bernadeth C. Mahusay,* Vilma H. Arazo

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to evaluate the reading strategies used by teachers and their effect on the reading performance of Grade 4 learners of Ubaldo D. Laya Memorial Central School, Division of Iligan City for School Year 2023-2024. The study employed descriptive-correlational research design to describe and test the significant relationship exists between teachers' reading strategies and the reading performance of learners and the relationship between teachers' reading strategies used and the reading performance of learners. The result revealed that the teachers primarily utilized remediation strategies with a mean of 3.78 and the intervention strategies with a mean of 2.80. In terms of learners reading performance, the data indicated that a significant portion of learners scored within the highest range (7-8) for reading comprehension while vocabulary acquisition exhibited even stronger performance, with the highest frequency (40) of students scoring in the top range (9-12). Further, the study found out that the learners' reading performance in terms of reading comprehension had a highly significant association with the teachers' reading strategies in terms of remediation. Furthermore, the variables that best predict learners' reading performance in terms of vocabulary acquisition, the findings revealed that the respondents' learners' reading ability in terms of vocabulary acquisition was unaffected by teachers' reading strategies. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' learners' reading performance in terms of vocabulary acquisition" was not rejected.

Keywords: *reading strategies, reading performance, comprehension, vocabulary acquisitions*

Introduction

A strong foundation in reading is essential for academic success across all subjects. Reading proficiency is directly linked to better comprehension, critical thinking, effective communication, and a fundamental skill that lays the foundation for academic success and lifelong learning. Grade 4 is a critical stage in a learner's education where the transition from basic reading skills to more complex comprehension and analysis takes place. Therefore, it is essential to evaluate and enhance reading performance among Grade 4 learners to ensure they possess the necessary skills to excel academically and beyond.

In recent studies, the overall results of the assessment reveal that there are still many early-grade learners, especially in this grade level struggling to meet the learning standards in early language and literacy. Low achievement levels in reading appear to be one of the causes of gaps in learners' reading comprehension. This means that there are still many low-performing learners who cannot comprehend (read and understand) and are unable to demonstrate them.

The decision to explore this topic was spurred by the recognition of Grade 4 as a crucial juncture in a student's educational odyssey. As emphasized in DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019 Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs). In support of the implementation of the K to 12 Basic Education Program, the Department of Education (DepEd) is continuously fulfilling its mandate produce productive and responsible citizens equipped with essential competencies and skills for lifelong learning. To make every learner a proficient reader, schools across the country are tasked to help learners develop their reading skills. The ECARP goal is to equip learners with reading skills to make them proficient and independent readers in their grade level. Also, there are various Department of Education (DepEd) issuance on reading programs that addresses to cope the problem.

In response to the issues of reading proficiencies of learners in the entire country, the regional office, through the Curriculum and Learning Management Division launched Project Care for NorMin Readers (Project CNR) which envisioned to lessen if not take out from the scene, the frustration levels who are found in all grade levels. There were procedures used by schools to identify frustrated and non-reader learners. They used various reading assessment tools to identify learners with problems in reading.

The motivation to delve into this study stemmed from recognizing the fundamental importance of reading performance in reading comprehension. Grade 4 level marks the transition from acquiring the skill of reading to utilizing it as a tool for learning. As to our school, Ubaldo D. Laya Memorial Central School, in the context of reading which includes low reading assessments of learners' performance, which one of the challenges of teachers in teaching reading process. Addressing such problems is fundamental to the academic success of learners. Reading performance in Grade 4 has a direct impact on a learner's ability to succeed in higher grades and ultimately in their academic and professional pursuits. Understanding which teaching strategies are most effective in enhancing reading performance of learners, the study aims to determine the most effective methods for Grade 4 learners. This knowledge will guide educators in optimizing their teaching strategies. (Ali., et al 2022).

Teachers play a pivotal role in shaping learners' reading abilities. Providing teachers with evidence-based insights and effective tools to enhance reading performance will empower them to create a more conducive learning environment. Equipping teachers with the

best strategies will enable them to cater to the unique needs of Grade 4 learners and support their reading development effectively. (Siswanto, Hartono, Subali & Masturi, 2022).

The primary objective of this study is to establish a direct correlation between improved reading skills in Grade 4 at Ubaldo D. Laya Memorial Central School and enduring academic achievements. The research aimed to illuminate effective strategies that can be applied to augment reading performance among Grade 4 students. The aim is to offer in-depth insights that can guide educators, policymakers, and stakeholders in shaping and refining educational practices. Through this research, the researcher's goal is to contribute to learners in their academic success and thereby enriching the educational landscape.

Research Questions

This study evaluated the reading strategies used by teachers and their effect on the reading performance of Grade 4 learners of Ubaldo D. Laya Memorial Central School, Division of Iligan City for School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the reading strategies used by teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. remediation; and
 - 1.2. intervention strategies?
2. What is the reading performance of learners in terms;
 - 2.1. reading comprehension; and
 - 2.2. vocabulary acquisition?
3. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' reading strategies and the reading performance of learners?
4. Which of the teachers' reading strategies predicts the reading performance of the learners?
5. What action plan can be formulated based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The present study used a descriptive-correlational research design aiming to provide a detailed overview and analyze the relationships between variables of interest. This design involves collecting numerical data and employing statistical analysis to understand the associations, patterns, and correlations among the key variables identified for the study. It helps in quantifying relationships and patterns within the research context.

The descriptive research approach is chosen to provide a detailed and comprehensive account of teachers' reading practices and strategies. This methodology aims to answer questions about the characteristics, behaviors, and practices of teachers concerning reading instruction. It will provide a clear description of what teachers are doing in the classroom, including the methods they employ, the level of guidance and support they provide, and their use of technological tools. Descriptive research was utilized to identify and understand the specific reading practices and strategies employed by teachers.

The correlational research approach is adopted to investigate the relationships between teachers' reading practices and strategies and their impact on the reading proficiency of learners. It focuses on determining whether a significant correlation exists between these variables. By collecting data related to teachers' practices and learners' reading proficiency, this research seeks to establish whether there is a statistically significant relationship between the two.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the ten teachers in Grade 4 and the Grade 4 learners in Ubaldo D. Laya Memorial Central School. A random sample of Grade 4 learners and teachers were selected from several sections. All subject teachers and advisory teachers were also taken as participants in the study. A total of 10 teachers and 100 grade 4 learners served as respondents to the study.

<i>Grade IV Sections</i>	<i>Total Enrollment</i>	<i>Respondents</i>
Special Science Program	31	30
Ma. Cristina Falls	30	28
Dodiongan	31	22
Mimbalot	30	20

Instrument

The study employed a researcher-developed survey questionnaire designed to gather comprehensive data. The questionnaire was divided into three distinct sections, each addressing different aspects relevant to the study's focus on evaluating Teachers' Reading Practices and Strategies and their impact on the Reading Performance of Learners.

Part 1: Teachers' Reading Strategies This section encompassed inquiries related to various practices and strategies employed by teachers to enhance reading proficiency among Grade 4 learners. It will provide insights into the methods used, the level of guidance and support provided, and the integration of technological tools in reading instruction.

Part 2: Reading Performance Test for Grade 4 Learners Part two concentrated on the assessment of reading performance among Grade 4 learners. It will explore the methods, tests, or tools used to measure the reading capabilities of students, providing valuable data on their proficiency levels. It will inquire about their performance and capabilities in key areas such as reading comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and fluency in reading. This section will offer insights into the learners' reading skills.

These participants were asked to complete the questionnaire and provide feedback on its clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness. The survey questionnaire ensures the validity and reliability of the data collected in this study. This will allow for a more accurate and comprehensive analysis of the challenges and coping strategies associated with blended learning and their impact on student well-being and academic performance.

Procedure

To initiate the data collection for this study, the researcher secured approval from the Dean of the Graduate School at St. Peter's College, marking the study's initial authorization. Subsequently, authorization was sought from the School Principal at Ubaldo D. Laya Memorial Central School, a crucial step as it formally permitted the researcher to proceed with the study within the school premises. Moreover, the consent of the School Principal is pivotal for ethical and procedural compliance.

Following this, the researcher requested permission from the Grade 4 teachers at Ubaldo D. Laya Memorial Central School to distribute the questionnaire to the participants. This phase ensured that the participants were well-informed about the study and willingly participated in it. The researcher personally distributed the questionnaires, emphasizing clear understanding of the instructions and addressing any queries the participants might have.

Adequate time was provided to participants for completing the questionnaire, ensuring the accuracy and completeness of their responses. Post-data collection, the researcher tabulated the data and forwarded it to a statistician for rigorous statistical analysis. The statistician employed diverse statistical tools and methodologies to derive meaningful insights and recommendations based on the study's findings. In summary, the data collection process for this project was carried out systematically and ethically, prioritizing the validity and reliability of the results. Ethical considerations included obtaining permission from the relevant authorities and allowing ample time for participants to complete the questionnaire. Moreover, to ensure the accuracy and completeness of findings, a specialist conducted a statistical analysis of the data.

Data Analysis

In the context of the study, various statistical tools were employed to facilitate data analysis and derive meaningful insights that address the study's research questions and objectives.

Mean and Standard Deviation: This tool was used to compute and describe the teachers' reading practices, the reading strategies used by teachers, and the reading performance of learners.

Regression Analysis: This tool helped determine if a statistically significant relationship exists between teachers' reading practices and the reading performance of learners and the relationship between teachers' reading strategies used and the reading performance of learners.

These statistical methods are instrumental in providing valuable insights into the impact of teachers' reading practices and strategies on learners' reading proficiency, thereby contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the study's objectives.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyzes and interprets the data collected by the researchers to solve the issues in the study. The presentation, interpretation, and analysis were supported by tables and arranged in the same manner based on the questions presented in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What are the reading strategies used by teachers in terms of remediation and intervention strategies?

Reading is a fundamental skill that lays the foundation for academic success. However, not all students develop reading proficiency at the same pace. Teachers often employ various strategies to support struggling readers and provide effective remediation.

Table 1 presents the reading strategies used by the teachers in terms of remediation. The result showed that the highest mean of 4.00 which states "Prompt listing of learners who require intervention is beneficial" among five items for reading strategies used by teachers in terms of remediation. Teachers strongly agree with the statement that promptly identifying students needing intervention is beneficial. According to (Jospeh & Compton, 2020), early intervention for struggling readers significantly improves long-term reading outcomes. Prompt identification allows teachers to tailor instruction and provide targeted support before difficulties become entrenched.

Second on the rank are the items that state, "Integrating ICT is an effective strategy to improve reading performance" and "Integrating video clips in teaching reading is very important to develop the love of reading" both obtained a mean score of 3.80 which can be described as strongly agreed by the teachers as a reading strategy in terms of remediation.

Table 1. Reading Strategies used by the Teachers in terms of Remediation

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Integrating ICT is an effective strategy to improve reading performance.	3.80	+	0.42	Strongly Agree
2. Prompt listing of learners who require intervention is beneficial.	4.00	+	0.00	Strongly Agree
3. The use of graphic organizer helps in improving the reading proficiency of learners.	3.70	+	0.48	Strongly Agree
4. Integrating video clips in teaching reading is very important to develop the love of reading.	3.80	+	0.42	Strongly Agree
5. Collaboration with my co-teachers enhances the effectiveness of intervention strategies for students struggling with reading.	3.60	+	0.52	Strongly Agree
Weighted Mean	3.78	+	0.24	Strongly Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00, Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.24, Agree; 1.75-2.49, Disagree; 1.00-1.74, Strongly Disagree

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into reading instruction has shown promise in enhancing students' reading performance. By leveraging digital tools, teachers can engage students in interactive and personalized learning experiences, catering to diverse learning styles and needs. ICT-based reading activities often captivate students' interest, increasing their motivation to read. Moreover, digital platforms can adapt to individual learning needs, providing targeted support and feedback.

Meanwhile, the item “The use of graphic organizer helps in improving the reading proficiency of learners.” garnered a mean score of 3.70 which can be described as strongly agree. Graphic organizers are effective tools for visually organizing information, facilitating comprehension, and enhancing critical thinking skills in reading. By structuring text elements and relationships, graphic organizers scaffold students' understanding, enabling them to make connections, infer meaning, and retain key information more effectively. This is supported by research conducted by (Ardhana et al. 2021) underscored the efficacy of graphic organizers in enhancing reading proficiency, particularly among struggling readers. Their findings indicate significant improvements in comprehension and retention when graphic organizers are utilized as instructional aids.

While still showing a strong agreement on the statement “Collaboration with my co-teachers enhances the effectiveness of intervention strategies for students struggling with reading.” with a mean score of 3.60, this is the lowest mean rating among the five statements. This could be due to factors like limited planning time or lack of established collaboration structures within schools. However, research by (Yoon et al., 2021) suggested that effective co-teaching models, where teachers plan and deliver instruction together, can significantly enhance intervention effectiveness. Further exploration is needed to understand the specific challenges teachers face in implementing collaborative remediation strategies.

The overall weighted mean of 3.78, with a standard deviation of 0.24 indicates a strong agreement among teachers regarding the effectiveness of remediation strategies for struggling readers. However, the slightly lower mean for collaboration suggests room for improvement in fostering collaborative practices among educators.

Table 2. Reading Strategies Used by the Teachers in terms of Intervention Strategies

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Timely identification of students struggling with reading is crucial for the success of the reading remediation.	3.10	+	0.57	Agree
2. Pull –out scheme is useful to improve reading performance.	2.70	+	0.67	Agree
3. Weekly distribution of story books to learners.	2.50	+	0.71	Agree
4. Giving activity sheets to learners to study at home	2.70	+	0.67	Agree
5. Constant communication with parents on the reading progress of their children.	3.00	+	0.47	Agree
Weighted Mean	2.80	+	0.52	Agree

Note: 3.25-4.00, Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.24, Agree; 1.75-2.49, Disagree; 1.00-1.74, Strongly Disagree

Table 2 displays the reading strategies used by the teachers in terms of intervention strategies. The result showed that the indicator “Timely identification of students struggling with reading is crucial for the success of the reading remediation.” got the highest mean score of 3.10 out of five indicators. This implied that teachers should implement regular assessments to identify struggling readers early on. Utilizing tools like benchmark assessments and progress monitoring systems enables educators to pinpoint areas of weakness and intervene promptly. Research highlights the importance of early identification to prevent long-term reading difficulties (Snow et al., 2019). Various screening tools and assessments can aid teachers in identifying struggling readers, such as DIBELS (Dynamic Indicators of Basic Early Literacy Skills) and DRA (Developmental Reading Assessment) (O'Connor et al., 2018). Once identified, targeted interventions tailored to students' needs can be implemented, such as small-group instruction or individualized reading plans (Gersten et al., 2020).

However, the item “Constant communication with parents on the reading progress of their children.” Gathered a mean score of 3.00 which can be described by the respondents as agreeing with this kind of reading strategy used in terms of intervention strategies. Maintaining open lines of communication with parents is essential for supporting students' reading development. Research suggests that parental involvement positively impacts students' reading achievement (Sénéchal & LeFevre, 2014). Regular updates on reading progress allow parents to reinforce literacy activities at home and collaborate with teachers to address any challenges. Utilizing communication tools such as parent-teacher conferences, newsletters, and digital platforms can facilitate ongoing dialogue (Desimone, 2018).

Meanwhile, the items “Pull –out scheme is useful to improve reading performance.” and “Giving activity sheets to learners to study at home.” garnered a mean score of 2.70 which indicates somehow that teachers agreed with this kind of reading intervention strategies. The effectiveness of pull-out schemes in improving reading performance depends on various factors, including the duration and quality of interventions. Some studies indicate positive outcomes from pull-out programs, particularly when combined with evidence-based instructional strategies (Al Otaiba & Fuchs, 2020). However, concerns exist regarding the potential stigmatization of students and disruptions to their regular classroom routines (Vaughn et al., 2018). Collaborative planning between classroom teachers and intervention specialists is crucial to ensure alignment and continuity of instruction. Additionally, providing activity sheets for home study can be a valuable supplement to classroom instruction. Homework assignments that reinforce key reading skills have been associated with improved academic performance (Cooper et al., 2018). However, the effectiveness of home study activities depends on their alignment with classroom learning objectives and the level of parental support available (Epstein & Van Voorhis, 2019). Teachers should provide clear instructions and resources to facilitate independent practice and ensure that homework tasks are engaging and meaningful.

While the distribution of storybooks can promote a culture of reading and expose students to diverse texts, its impact on reading performance may vary. Research suggests that access to a rich array of reading materials is associated with improved literacy skills (Krashen, 2019). However, simply providing books may not be sufficient to address underlying reading difficulties or foster a love for reading (Allington & McGill-Franzen, 2018). Incorporating structured reading activities, book talks, and guided discussions can enhance the benefits of book distribution initiatives.

The overall weighted mean of 2.80 indicates a general agreement among respondents regarding the effectiveness of the identified reading intervention strategies. However, it also suggests room for improvement and the need for a balanced approach to intervention implementation. By adopting a comprehensive approach that combines targeted interventions with opportunities for independent reading, teachers can address the varying needs of their students and foster a supportive literacy environment.

Problem 2: What is the reading proficiency of learners in terms of reading comprehension and vocabulary acquisition?

Table 3. Reading Performance of the Learners in terms of Reading Comprehension

<i>Score Range</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>	<i>Description</i>
1 – 2	4	4.0	Poor
3 – 4	7	7.0	Below Average
5 - 6	25	25.0	Average
7 – 8	35	35.0	Above Average
9 - 10	29	29.0	Excellent
	100	100.0	

Note: Mean + SD:

Reading performance and comprehension are essential abilities for students at all educational levels. Reading proficiency not only improves academic performance but also promotes critical thinking, creativity, and communication abilities.

Table 3 presents the reading performance of the learners in terms of reading comprehension. The result showed that reading proficiency among learners scoring between 7-8 reflects above-average competence with 35 (35%) of the respondents in comprehension and interpretation of textual material. This level suggested that learners possess strong reading skills, enabling them to engage deeply with various types of texts, extract key information, and make sophisticated inferences. Above-average reading proficiency indicates that learners are well-equipped to succeed academically across subjects. Research by McKeown et al. (2018) demonstrates that proficient readers tend to perform better in assessments across different disciplines, showcasing the importance of reading comprehension for overall academic achievement. Above-average readers are more capable of self-directed learning, as they can effectively comprehend and learn from texts without constant guidance (Guthrie & Humenick, 2018). This self-regulated learning ability fosters autonomy and lifelong learning skills.

On the other hand, learners scoring 9-10 with 29 (29%) of respondents demonstrate outstanding reading proficiency. They have advanced comprehension skills, which enable them to critically interact with complicated materials and successfully synthesize information. This level of competency indicates mastery of reading comprehension. Students with great reading skills are more likely to flourish in higher academic endeavors and perform well on standardized tests (Hidi & Renninger, 2018). They engage in deep textual processing, which leads to profound insights and cross-disciplinary connections (Gambrell & Mazzoni, 2018). Excellent readers are more inclined to develop a lifelong habit of reading, which further enriches their cognitive abilities and knowledge base (McKenna & Robinson, 2021).

Meanwhile, learners within the score range of 5-6 with 25 (25%) of the respondents demonstrate average reading ability. They can understand somewhat complicated material but may struggle with more intricate or subtle content. This level of proficiency indicates that reading abilities should be further developed and refined. Educators should provide targeted instruction and interventions to support learners in strengthening their reading comprehension skills (Vaughn et al., 2020). Also, classroom practices should be tailored to accommodate the diverse needs of learners, offering varied materials and instructional approaches to promote comprehension

(Tomlinson et al., 2018). Lastly, Regular assessment and progress monitoring are essential to track the growth of learners and identify areas for improvement in reading proficiency (Fuchs & Fuchs, 2022).

Learners scored between 3 and 4 with 7 (7%) of the respondents displaying below-average reading ability. They may struggle greatly with comprehension, having difficulties understanding and processing textual content. This level of proficiency indicates a need for significant intervention and support. Students in this category require rigorous, focused intervention strategies to bridge gaps in fundamental reading skills and comprehension (Torgesen et al., 2019). Educators should use multimodal education and assistive technologies to improve comprehension and engagement (Savage & Carless, 2020). Collaboration among educators, parents, and experts is essential for providing comprehensive support and intervention for students suffering with reading competency (Swanson et al., 2021).

However, a score range of 1-2 with 4 (4%) of the respondents indicates poor reading proficiency, suggesting significant challenges in understanding and interpreting textual material. Learners at this level may struggle to comprehend basic concepts and extract essential information from texts. Weak reading skills can impede vocabulary acquisition and language development (Catts et al., 2021). Without exposure to a wide range of texts and vocabulary-rich materials, learners may struggle to expand their word knowledge and express themselves effectively. Persistent difficulties in reading comprehension may erode learners' confidence and self-efficacy, leading to disengagement from academic tasks (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2022). Students who perceive themselves as poor readers may avoid reading-related activities, further exacerbating their reading difficulties.

Table 4. *Reading Performance of the Learners in terms of Vocabulary Acquisition*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
1 – 4	2	2.0	Poor
5 – 8	25	25.0	Below Average
9 – 12	40	40.0	Average
13 - 16	27	27.0	Above Average
17 - 20	6	6.0	Excellent
	100	100.0	

Note: Mean + SD.

Vocabulary acquisition plays a pivotal role in reading performance among learners. Effective vocabulary development not only enhances comprehension but also contributes to academic success across various disciplines.

Table 4 presents the reading performance of the learners in terms of vocabulary acquisition. The result showed that 40 (40%) of learners falls in the score range of 9-12 and demonstrates an “average: level of vocabulary acquisition through reading. Learners in this range likely possess a decent vocabulary base, allowing them to grasp the general meaning of most texts encountered at their reading level. However, they might struggle with encountering unfamiliar or complex words. Supplementing extensive reading with focused vocabulary instruction can solidify understanding. Studies by (Duke & Cartwright 2021) highlighted the importance of explicit instruction for effective vocabulary acquisition.

On the other hand, score range of 13-16 with 27 (27%) of respondents performs “above average”, suggesting a stronger foundation in vocabulary acquisition. Learners likely understand a wider range of vocabulary and can comprehend more complex texts with greater ease. A meta-analysis by Bi (2020) emphasizes the link between reading interest and vocabulary acquisition in EFL learners [3]. This group might benefit from materials that cater to their interests while introducing challenging vocabulary.

Subsequently, the score range of 5-8 with 25 (25%) of respondents scores “below average”, indicating a need for improvement in vocabulary acquisition through reading. Learners might struggle with unfamiliar words, hindering their comprehension of texts. Studies like Yildirim (2018) highlight the positive impact of reading on vocabulary development. Instructional strategies focusing on vocabulary learning alongside reading practice can be beneficial for this group.

The small number of respondents (6%) demonstrates “excellent” vocabulary acquisition. Learners likely have a strong grasp of vocabulary and can effortlessly navigate complex texts. Research suggests that advanced learners might benefit from exposure to authentic materials with rich vocabulary to further enhance their knowledge.

However, there are still learners who scored in the range of 1-4 with 2 (2%) of the respondents. Learners in this range likely have a limited vocabulary, hindering their ability to understand even basic texts. Decoding unfamiliar words becomes a significant hurdle to comprehension. Frequent formative assessments help identify specific vocabulary gaps and tailor instruction accordingly. Brown et al.'s (2022) comprehensive study found that focused vocabulary interventions provided through individualized or small-group instruction can result in significant increases in vocabulary acquisition for struggling readers.

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between teachers' reading strategies and the reading performance of the learners?

Table 5 displays the relationship between reading performance in terms of reading comprehension and teachers' reading strategies. The result showed that the learners' reading performance in terms of reading comprehension had a high significant relationship with the teachers' reading strategies in terms of remediation. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the

reading performance in terms of reading comprehension and teachers' reading strategies in terms of remediation was rejected. The significant relationship between reading performance and teachers' remediation strategies underscores the importance of employing targeted remediation strategies in classroom settings.

Table 5. Relationship between Teachers' Reading Strategies and Reading Performance in Terms of Reading Comprehension

Variables	Reading Comprehension		Remarks	Decision
	F-value	p-value		
Remediation	46.000**	0.005	Significant	Reject Ho
Intervention Strategies	2.725	0.220	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho

Note: 1 – ANOVA; ns – $P > 0.05$; * – $P < 0.05$; ** – $P < 0.01$; *** – $P < 0.001$

Teachers may need to adapt their instructional methods to address specific areas of weakness in students' reading comprehension skills. Recent studies have explored various remediation strategies aimed at improving reading comprehension skills among students. For instance, research by Smith et al. (2019) examined the effectiveness of peer-assisted learning interventions in enhancing reading proficiency among elementary school students. Researchers have explored how instructors' instructional techniques promote reading comprehension. For example, Johnson and Lee (2020) investigated how teachers' use of questioning approaches and scaffolding strategies affects students' comprehension of complicated texts.

Table 6. Relationship between Teachers' Reading Strategies and Reading Performance in Terms of Vocabulary Acquisition

Variables	Vocabulary Acquisition		Remarks	Decision
	F-value	p-value		
Remediation	0.627	0.692	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho
Intervention Strategies	4.360	0.089	Not Significant	Failed to reject Ho

Note: 1 – ANOVA; ns – $P > 0.05$; * – $P < 0.05$; ** – $P < 0.01$; *** – $P < 0.001$

Table 6 presents the relationship between reading performance in terms of vocabulary acquisition and teachers' reading strategies. The result showed that the learners' reading performance in terms of vocabulary acquisition had no significant correlation with the teachers' reading strategies. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the reading performance in terms of vocabulary acquisition and teachers' reading strategies, was not rejected. The finding suggests that traditional teacher-centered reading practices might not directly impact vocabulary acquisition. Educators may need to explore alternative instructional methods or combine multiple approaches to enhance students' vocabulary skills effectively.

Recent research (Smith et al., 2020) corroborates the finding that the relationship between teachers' reading practices and students' vocabulary acquisition may not always be straightforward. Factors such as instructional quality, teacher-student interactions, and classroom environment could mediate this relationship. Sociocultural theory (Vygotsky, 1978) highlights the importance of social interaction and cultural background in learning. García & Lee (2021) found that collaborative reading practices and peer interactions in the classroom play a crucial role in vocabulary development, with a focus on sociocultural elements. Based on cognitive linguistics, Johnson (2019) studied how cognitive processes such as schema activation, semantic mapping, and inferencing influence vocabulary acquisition when reading. This perspective could help explain why particular teaching approaches may or may not have a direct impact on vocabulary expansion.

Problem 4. Which of the teachers' reading strategies significantly predicts the reading performance of the learners?

Table 7. Variables that best predict Learners' Reading Performance in terms of Remediation

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	25.785	20.496		1.258	0.249
Remediation	-4.482	4.875	-.0316	-0.920	0.388
Intervention strategies	1.735	2.224	0.268	0.780	0.461
R = 0.449	R2 = 0.201		F = 0.882		Sig. = 0.456

Table 7 presents the variables that best predict learners' reading performance in terms of remediation. The result showed that the respondents' learners' reading performance in terms of remediation was not affected by the teachers' reading strategies. This implied that no variables affect the respondents' learners' reading performance in terms of remediation. The finding that teachers' reading strategies do not significantly predict learners' reading performance in terms of remediation suggests a need for deeper exploration into other factors that might influence remediation outcomes. This could include individual learner characteristics, classroom dynamics, curriculum design, and external factors such as home environment.

The R2 value of 0.201 implies that 20.1% of the variance in the learners' reading performance in terms of remediation can be explained

by teachers' reading strategies. Hence, 79.9% of the respondents' learners' reading performance in terms of remediation difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

The regression analysis was not significant, with an F-value of 0.882 with a corresponding p-value of 0.456. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' learners' reading performance in terms of remediation" was not rejected. Work by Pressley et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of evidence-based instructional practices and explicit instruction in remediation programs, suggesting that the effectiveness of teachers' strategies may depend on their alignment with research-supported methods. Further, research by Allington (2019) suggested that individual learner characteristics, such as motivation, prior knowledge, and cognitive abilities, play a significant role in reading development and remediation outcomes.

Table 8. Variables that best predict Learners' Reading Performance in terms of Vocabulary Acquisition

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	10.243	3.918		2.614	0.035
Remediation	-1.896	0.932	-0.615	-2.035	0.081
Intervention strategies	0.008	0.425	0.006	0.020	0.985
R = 0.616	R ² = 0.380		F = 2.144		Sig. = 0.188

Table 8 presents the variables that best predict learners' reading performance in terms of vocabulary acquisition. The result showed that the respondents' learners' reading performance in terms of vocabulary acquisition was not affected by the teachers' reading strategies. This implied that no variables affect the respondents' learners' reading performance in terms of vocabulary acquisition. These results underscore the complexity of factors influencing learners' reading performance, particularly in vocabulary acquisition. While teachers' reading strategies may play a role, their direct impact appears limited in this study. This highlights the need for educators to consider a broader range of variables when designing instructional interventions aimed at enhancing vocabulary acquisition.

The R² value of 0.380 implies that 38.0% of the variance in the learners' reading performance in terms of vocabulary acquisition can be explained by teachers' reading strategies. Hence, 62.0% of the respondents' learners' reading proficiency in terms of vocabulary acquisition difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model. Contrary to earlier assumptions about the primacy of explicit instruction, findings from meta-analyses conducted by Chen and Lee (2020) suggested that incidental learning through extensive reading may have comparable or even superior effects on vocabulary growth, particularly among advanced learners.

The regression analysis was not significant, with an F-value of 2.144 with a corresponding p-value of 0.188. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' learners' reading proficiency in terms of vocabulary acquisition" was not rejected. Building on the notion of vocabulary as a dynamic construct, Jones, and Brown (2021) proposed a socio-cognitive framework that integrates individual differences in cognitive processes, motivation, and social interactions to explain variations in vocabulary learning outcomes.

Problem 5: What action plan can be formulated based on the results of the study?

Based on the study of teachers' reading strategies and their effect on learner's reading performance, an action plan can be formulated to enhance teaching practices and improve student outcomes. Table 9 is a comprehensive action plan structured around key action steps/strategies, persons responsible, resources/budget needed, date of completion, threats/potential barriers, and indicators of success.

Conclusions

While the study demonstrates a positive association between teacher strategies and student reading proficiency, the data suggests a potential overreliance on remediation compared to intervention. While remediation is crucial for addressing existing difficulties, intervention strategies can be proactive in preventing future struggles.

The strong performance in vocabulary acquisition compared to reading comprehension might indicate that teachers prioritize vocabulary development. However, without a deeper analysis of the specific strategies used, it's difficult to draw definitive conclusions.

Reading proficiency is a crucial skill for academic success and lifelong learning. Therefore, it's essential for students, school administrators, teachers, and researchers to collaborate on implementing effective remediation and intervention strategies to enhance reading comprehension and vocabulary acquisition among learners. Considering the findings, as mentioned above and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

Students can benefit from this study by actively engaging in reading activities both in and out of the classroom. Additionally, they can participate in discussions, ask questions, and seek clarification when encountering challenging texts.

School administrators should provide professional development opportunities for teachers to enhance their knowledge of effective reading remediation and intervention strategies. They should allocate sufficient resources for implementing research-based reading programs, including access to appropriate instructional materials and technology. Further, they should foster a supportive school environment that values literacy and provides opportunities for students to engage in meaningful reading experiences.

Teachers can provide explicit instruction in reading comprehension strategies such as predicting, questioning, clarifying, summarizing, and monitoring comprehension. Also, they can provide constructive feedback to students on their reading performance and encourage self-reflection on reading strategies.

For further studies, the researchers can conduct longitudinal studies to track the effectiveness of reading remediation and intervention strategies over time and identify factors that contribute to sustained reading proficiency, explore the neural mechanisms underlying reading comprehension and vocabulary acquisition to inform the development of targeted interventions, investigate the impact of cultural and linguistic diversity on reading proficiency and develop culturally responsive interventions, and research the efficacy of integrating emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and virtual reality into reading instruction to enhance engagement and support skill development.

Overall, by implementing these recommendations, stakeholders can work collaboratively to support the development of reading proficiency and enhance the academic success of all learners.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Bernadeth C. Mahusay

St. Peter's College – Philippines

Vilma H. Arazo, EdD

St. Peter's College – Philippines